

An evolutionary strategic weight manipulation approach for multi-attribute decision making: TOPSIS method

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Abstract

Weight information of the attributes plays a pivotal role in multi-attribute decision making (MADM) problems. Oftentimes, a decision maker may try to manipulate this weight information to persuade a particular rank order of the alternatives of his/her interest. In the literature, this type of manipulation is known as strategic manipulation of the weight information. In this study, we consider the manipulation of weight information strategically in a TOPSIS MADM method under two scenarios: (1) *completely unknown weight information* i.e. the decision maker does not provide any weight information; (2) *incomplete weight information* i.e. the decision maker provides only partial preference information over the attributes. This weight manipulation problem is formulated as a mixed integer non-linear programming (MINLP) problem which is highly constrained. Therefore, for solving the MINLP model, a genetic algorithm based solution procedure is developed. A practical example is presented to illustrate the strategic manipulation procedure.

1. Introduction

In tactical decision making, the decision situations are often characterized by a discrete set of alternatives and the performance of each alternative from the set of alternatives is usually measured over a finite set of conflicting attributes [1]. This class of decision making problems is termed as the multi-attribute decision making (MADM) problem. Thus far, the literature has reported various methods for solving this class of problems, such as, AHP [2], TOPSIS [1], PROMETHEE [3], ELECTRE [4], QUALIFLEX [5], MULTIMOORA [6], VIKOR [7], etc.

In the specialized literature several schemes have been proposed either to collect or to generate weights of the attributes and used in MADM methods. They can be broadly classified into three categories [15]:

1. *subjective approach*: weights of the attributes are determined based on the decision maker's subjective preference information over the attributes [16, 22, 24, 25, 26]

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2. *objective approach*: weights of the attributes are generated directly from the decision matrix [1, 27, 28, 29].
3. *integrated approach*: weights of the attributes are generated by utilizing subjective preference information given by the decision maker's with objective information decision matrix [30, 31, 32, 33].

Undoubtedly, different weight generation methods, mentioned above may yield different weight vectors for the same decision making problem and that may change the final decision outcome of the MADM method, as in practice the weights are highly sensitive to the decision information [34]. That characteristic of the weight information makes it vulnerable to manipulation in MADM problems. Sometimes, a decision maker may deliberately alter his/her weight information to obtain a particular ranking of some alternatives of interest. This kind of manipulation in weight information is called the *strategic manipulation* or *non-cooperative behavior* [35]. Yager [36, 37] has addressed the strategic manipulation of decision information by individual agents in multi-agents group decision making under t -norm [36] and uninorm [37], and Yager has suggested some mechanisms for forming group opinions in the presence of such strategic manipulations. Dong et al. [38] proposed a consensus-reaching framework to manage the non-cooperative behavior of the decision makers, while Palomares et al. [39] proposed a fuzzy clustering mechanism to detect and manage non-cooperative behavior in large-scale group decision making. For managing non-cooperative behaviors with minority opinions in the process of reaching consensus, Xu et al. [40] developed a new model and applied it in a large-scale group decision making problem in the context of emergency situations. Recently, Dong et al. [35] introduced the concept of a ranking range of an alternative, and they proposed a mixed 0 – 1 linear programming model to set the attributes' weights strategically with the ranking of the alternatives based on the weighted average and the ordered weighted average operators. In their model, the weight is searched in an $(n - 1)$ dimensional simplex $\{w_i \geq 0 | \sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1\}$ and the range is computed by optimizing a mixed 0 – 1 linear programming model. In many cases, the optimality condition forces many components of the optimal weights to tend to zero which means that corresponding criteria information has not been considered in the decision models. In practice, all the attributes have some importance. None of them are redundant. Therefore, to recognize the importance of each attribute, one can reserve a certain amount of importance for each criterion.

Sometimes, a decision maker can provide an incomplete set of preferences over the attributes' weight information [41]. Such an incomplete set of preference information can be used to determine the complete weight information by coupling it with decision information and optimizing the alternatives performance [42, 43]. This strategy has been used in the recent extant literature [44, 45, 46, 47]. As the preference information is a vital part of the information provided, special care is necessary when dealing with the strategic manipulation of the weight information in MADM.

Amongst the suite of MADM techniques previously mentioned, the Technique of Order Preference

by Similarity to Ideal Solution or TOPSIS, proposed by Hwang and Yoon [1], is one of the most popular MADM methods used to determine the rank order of the alternatives. Since its inception, it has been widely used to solve practical problems found in different fields [8, 9], and TOPSIS has gained popularity for its simplicity [10, 11, 12, 13]. It has been reported that TOPSIS is the second most popular MADM method after AHP [14, 13].

A key component in the implementation of TOPSIS method to find the ranking order of the alternatives is the weight information of the attributes. Hence, this paper treats the strategic manipulation of weight information in TOPSIS when a decision maker provides incomplete preference information about the weight space. We then formulate the ranking range finding problem as a mixed 0 – 1 non-linear programming problem, following Dong et al. [35] model, but such a model did not consider the weight preference information and just followed simple aggregation operators: weighted arithmetic mean, and ordered weighted arithmetic mean based decision models. The solution of such a non-linear model is quite hard task because the complexity of the model increase with the increase in the number of alternatives. Therefore, evolutionary algorithmic (EA) approaches provide global best solution of this kind of non-linear integer programming problem. Genetic algorithms (GAs) are outstanding class in the family of EAs and GA has been applied widely in practical applications [49, 54]. Therefore, we propose the use of a GA approach to solve this highly constrained optimization problem. Finally, we formulate the strategic weight manipulation model as a mixed 0 – 1 non-linear programming problem and analyze its performance.

The paper is set as follows. In Section 2, we revise the steps of TOPSIS method and the strategic weight manipulation model proposed by Dong et al.[35]. In Section 3, we develop the models for finding the ranking range and strategic weight manipulation for TOPSIS under the given incomplete weight information, which is a non-linear 0 – 1 mixed programming problem. Section 4 describes the GA based solution strategy of solving the non-linear 0 – 1 mixed programming models (13) and (14). A practical problem is presented in Section 5 to validate the proposed weight manipulation model. Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Preliminaries

2.1. TOPSIS

TOPSIS was first presented by Hwang and Yoon [1], in their seminal work, “Multiple attribute decision making methods and applications: A state of the art survey” in 1981. Since then, it has been applied widely in solving many practical MADM problems and emerged as a very popular MADM method. TOPSIS utilizes the idea of compromise solution to rank the alternatives. In other words, TOPSIS aids the decision maker to make the ranking order of the alternatives by deriving compromise

indexes based on the distances of the alternatives from positive ideal solution (PIS) and negative ideal solution (NIS).

TOPSIS requires two types of information from the user to find the ranking of the alternatives. The first type is decision information (a.k.a. decision matrix) of the alternatives against a predefined set of the performance measurement criteria. The second type of information is the relative importance of the criteria. Mathematically, the description of the decision information and weight information is as follows:

- A finite set of $m(\geq 2)$ alternatives: $X = \{x_i | i \in I\}$, where $I = \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$
- A fixed set of criteria: $C = \{C_j | j \in J\}$ where $J = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$
- The weight vector of the criteria: $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)$ such that $w_j > 0$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$.
- The alternatives are assessed over criteria and evaluations are summarized in the following decision matrix:

$$D = \begin{matrix} & C_1 & C_2 & \cdots & C_n \\ \begin{matrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_m \end{matrix} & \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \cdots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \cdots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \cdots & a_{mn} \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

where a_{ij} denotes the performance measure of the alternative x_i against the criteria C_j .

Based on the above information, TOPSIS can rank the alternatives by using the following steps:

Step 1 Normalization of decision matrix. The normalized decision matrix $R = (r_{ij})_{m \times n}$ is computed as follows: For benefit attributes:

$$r_{ij} = \frac{a_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m a_{ij}^2}} \quad (1)$$

For cost attributes:

$$r_{ij} = \frac{1/a_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m 1/a_{ij}^2}} \quad (2)$$

Step 2 Computation of weighted normalized decision matrix. The weighted normalized decision matrix $V = (v_{ij})_{m \times n}$ is computed as follows:

$$v_{ij} = w_j * r_{ij} \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, m, j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (3)$$

Step 3 Determination of positive ideal solution and negative ideal solutions:

$$PIS = (v_1^+, v_2^+, \dots, v_n^+) = ((\max_i v_{ij} : j \in C'), (\min_i v_{ij} : j \in C'')) \quad (4)$$

$$NIS = (v_1^-, v_2^-, \dots, v_n^-) = ((\min_i v_{ij} : j \in C'), (\max_i v_{ij} : j \in C'')) \quad (5)$$

where C' denotes the set of benefit criteria and C'' is the set of cost criteria.

Step 4 Computation of separation measures based on the n -dimensional Euclidean distance. The separation measure of the alternative A_i from PIS is computed as follows:

$$D_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_i^+)^2} \quad (6)$$

Similarly the separation measure from NIS is computed as follows:

$$D_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_i^-)^2} \quad (7)$$

Step 5 Computation of relative closeness coefficient to the ideal solutions. For an alternative A_i , the relative closeness coefficient is defined as follows:

$$C_i = \frac{D_i^-}{D_i^+ + D_i^-} \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (8)$$

Step 6 Based on the relative closeness coefficient alternatives are ranked. The lesser value of relative closeness coefficient makes the better rank of the alternative.

2.2. Strategic manipulation of weight

Often-times decision maker may attempt to manipulate their preference to come up with the results of his/her interest in the decision-making process. Such scenarios are referred to as strategic manipulation (*non-cooperative behaviour* in the context of group decision-making) in the decision making process. Such phenomena are also common in the context of MADM, where different types of preference information are provided by the decision maker. When the decision maker only attempts to manipulate preference information of the attributes' weight strategically to favour certain outcome in MADM process, we termed it as strategic manipulation of the weight information in MADM process. Note that such strategic manipulation of weight in the decision-making process may also be cast as a decision maker's preference learning problem. Thus it might be helpful in modelling decision maker's preference.

Decision maker being the source of preference information, ambiguity in the attributes weight information is inherent in decision-making. Further, the incomplete knowledge about weight information may lead to variability and imprecision in the final outcomes in the decision making, which may trigger several questions in decision maker's mind about the different consequences. For example, decision maker may interested to know, what are best possible achievable rank for an alternative under the given set of preferences on the weight, what would be the impact on the highest achievable rank by an alternative if he/she restricts weight of a particular attribute, what should be the weight vector to set a particular ranking order of the alternatives, how much improvement in the rank order of a particular alternative possible by changing weight information and so on. Strategic manipulation framework allow us to answer such questions from the decision maker, regarding the consequences of the decision outcomes. Thus, it equips the decision maker with the holistic perspectives and deeper insight on the possible consequences of the decision analysis.

In this section, we briefly introduce the concept of strategic manipulation of weight model proposed by Dong et al. [35]. The notion of ranking range of the alternative is the fundamental construct of strategic weight manipulation. We now describe it briefly.

Let $F(x_i)$ be the final decision evaluation of alternative x_i , obtained by a decision method (it may obtain by utilizing an aggregation operator or any other MADM technique such as TOPSIS, VIKOR, or ELECTRE). We further assume that $F(x_i), \forall i \in I$ provides the rank order of the alternatives' set X . Then, the rank positions of the alternatives induced by the final evaluations $F(x_i)$ can be defined as follows:

Definition 1. [35] Let $rp(x_k)$ be the ranking position of alternative x_k . Then,

$$rp(x_k) = |\{x_i | F(x_i) > F(x_k) \ i \in I\}| + 1 \quad (9)$$

where $|X|$ denotes the cardinality of the set X .

Clearly, $F(x_i)$ not only depends on the decision matrix D and weight information w , but also it depends on the parameters associated with the decision making methods. For example, in TOPSIS, different distance metrics may produce different results and the distance metric is a decision making parameter. When we fix all the parameters of the decision making methods with decision matrix D , the final decision evaluation of the alternatives depends only on the weight information. To emphasize this fact, we denote $F(x_i)$ as $F_w(x_i)$. The variation in w allows us to produce different rank positions of the same alternative. The rank position range of an alternative under the variation of weight information can be defined as follows:

Definition 2. [35] The ranking range of the alternative x_i is given by $RR(x_i) = [rp^{\min}(x_i), rp^{\max}(x_i)]$ with $rp^{\min}(x_i) = \min_{w \in W} F_w(x_i)$, $rp^{\max}(x_i) = \max_{w \in W} F_w(x_i)$ and $W = \{(w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n) | \sum_{j=1}^n w_j =$

1 and $w_j > 0 \forall j \in J$.

Basically, the ranking range provides us with the best and worst rank of an alternative under a weight variation over the weight space W . To find the ranking range of an alternative, we can formulate a mixed 0 – 1 programming problem as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{maximize} && \sum_{i=1}^m y_i + 1 \\
& \text{s.t.} && \begin{cases} F_w(x_i) > F_w(x_k) - (1 - y_i)M, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \\ F_w(x_i) \leq F_w(x_k) + y_i M, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \\ \sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1 \\ 0 \leq w_j \leq 1 \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n \\ y_i = 1 \text{ or } 0 \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \end{cases}
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

The solution to the optimization model of Eq. (10) provides us with the best rank of the alternative. The worst rank of the alternative can be found by solving model Eq. (10) with a minimization of the objective function, i.e., $\min \sum_{i=1}^m y_i + 1$.

We now describe the strategic manipulation of the weight information through the mixed 0 – 1 programming problem. Let $w^g = (w_1^g, w_2^g, \dots, w_n^g)$ be the given weighting vector of the attributes of an MADM problem. We assume that the decision maker intends to manipulate the rank order of the alternatives' set: $X = \{x_{i_1}, \dots, x_{i_l}\}$. Suppose $\{rp^*(x_{i_1}), \dots, rp^*(x_{i_l})\}$ is the desired rank position of the manipulated alternatives intended by the decision maker.

Let $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)$ be the decision maker's strategic weight vector used to manipulate the rank position of the alternatives $\{x_{i_1}, \dots, x_{i_l}\}$. The decision maker's intention is to manipulate the weight vector in such a way that it deviates minimally from the given weight vector w_g . This optimization strategy can be formulated in the following optimization model:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{minimization} && d(w, w^g) \\
& \text{s.t.} && \begin{cases} F_w(x_i) > F_w(x_k) - (1 - y_{ik})M, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m, \quad k = i_1, i_2, \dots, i_l \\ F_w(x_i) > F_w(x_k) + y_{ik}M, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m, \quad k = i_1, i_2, \dots, i_l \\ \sum_{i=1}^m y_{ik} + 1 = rp^*(x_k), \quad k = i_1, i_2, \dots, i_l \\ \sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1, \\ 0 \leq w_j \leq 1, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n \\ y_{ik} = 1 \text{ or } 0 \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m, \quad k = i_1, i_2, \dots, i_l \end{cases}
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

where $d : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ is a distance metric that measures the deviation in the weight information. Here, \mathbb{R}^+ denotes the non-negative, real numbers. This generic model can strategically manipulate the weight information in the MADM methods such as TOPSIS, VIKOR, QUALIFLEX, ELECTRE, PROMETHEE, and any aggregation function based MADM approaches. When we choose F_w as a weighted arithmetic mean and the distance metric as a Hamming distance, the model (11) becomes Dong et. al's strategic manipulation of weights under a weighted arithmetic based final decision evaluation. Therefore, the weight manipulation model (11) generalizes the model presented in Dong et al.[35].

3. Strategic manipulation of attributes weight in TOPSIS

In this section, we illustrate the strategic manipulation of the weights in the TOPSIS MADM model.

Weight information of attributes plays a pivotal role in the ranking of the alternatives by TOPSIS. Different weight sources produce different rank order outcomes of the TOPSIS method albeit using the same decision information when all the other parameters associated with the TOPSIS model are kept constant [34]. The choice of the proper weight of the attributes is critical to the accuracy of TOPSIS [48]. This fact makes the weight information more susceptible to changes when manipulating the ranking of the alternatives.

In model (11), we have not added any information regarding the weight except the normalization condition that the weight vector belongs to the n-dimensional simplex. Without any additional weight information, sometimes the optimization model (11) neglects the decision information under one or many attributes by setting the criteria to assume zero weight values. That means that the decision information under those criteria is not considered when making the final decision, which is clearly not desirable. As all the attributes under consideration are important and none of them are redundant, we should consider all of the attributes as being more or less equally important.

Further, the inherent subjectivity in human cognition and the uncertainty present in actual decision making situations might lead to incomplete information about the attribute weights. Such incomplete information on the attributes weights can be expressed as linear inequalities, such as, ranking, interval description, and so on [41]. Let Q_w be the incomplete weight information about the attributes. The incomplete information can then be expressed in the following form [41]:

- Case-I: A weak ranking: $Q_w = \{w_{j_1} \leq w_{j_2} : j_1, j_2 \in J\}$;
- Case-II: A strict ranking: $Q_w = \{w_{j_1} - w_{j_2} \geq \alpha_{j_1, j_2} : j_1, j_2 \in J \ \& \ \alpha_{j_1, j_2} > 0\}$;
- Case-III: A ranking of differences: $Q_w = \{w_{j_1} - w_{j_2} \leq w_{j_3} - w_{j_4} : j_1, j_2, j_3, j_4 \in J \ \& \ \forall j_2 \neq j_3 \neq j_4\}$;
- Case-IV: A ranking with multiples: $Q_w = \{w_{j_1} \geq \alpha_{j_1} w_{j_2} : j_1, j_2 \in J, \ \& \ 0 \leq \alpha_{j_1} \leq 1\}$;
- Case-V: An interval form: $\{\alpha_j \leq w_j \leq \beta_j : j \in J \ \& \ 0 \leq \alpha_j \leq \beta_j\}$.

Park et al. [41] provided a detailed description of cases (I - V) as applied to practical decision making problems. Here, we assume that incomplete information about the attributes is provided by the decision maker. The partial preference information of the weight vectors is included in the models when finding the ranking range and strategic weights to find the strategic weight vector which preserves the decision maker's preference.

In TOPSIS, the final evaluation function of any alternative $F_w(x_i)$ is given by the closeness coefficient C_i . To emphasize the dependence of C_i on w_i , we denote it by $C_w(x_i)$. Incorporating the incomplete weight information in the optimization model for finding the ranking range of alternative x_i , leads us to

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{maximize} && \sum_{i=1}^m y_i + 1 \\
& \text{s.t.} && \begin{cases} C_w(x_i) > C_w(x_k) - (1 - y_i)M & i = 1, 2, \dots, m \\ C_w(x_i) \leq C_w(x_k) + y_i M & i = 1, 2, \dots, m \\ \sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1 \\ 0 \leq w_j \leq 1 & j = 1, 2, \dots, n \\ w \in Q_w \\ y_i = 1 \text{ or } 0 & i = 1, 2, \dots, m \\ w_i \geq \beta_i; & i = 1, 2, \dots, m \end{cases} \tag{12}
\end{aligned}$$

The last constraint ensures that none of the components of the optimal weight vector will be with

zero labels, i.e., no attribute is redundant. Plugging the values of $C_w(x_i)$ into model (12), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
& \max \sum_{i=1}^m y_i + 1 \\
& \text{s.t.} \left\{ \begin{array}{l}
\frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - NI_j)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - NI_j)^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - PI_j)^2}} > \\
\frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - NI_j)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - NI_j)^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - PI_j)^2}} - (1 - y_i)M \\
i = 1, 2, \dots, m \\
\frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - NI_j)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - NI_j)^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - PI_j)^2}} \leq \\
\frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - NI_j)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - NI_j)^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - PI_j)^2}} + y_iM \\
i = 1, 2, \dots, m \\
\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1 \\
0 \leq w_j \leq 1 \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n \\
w \in Q_w \\
y_i = 1 \text{ or } 0 \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \\
w_i \geq \beta_i; i = 1, 2, \dots, m
\end{array} \right. \tag{13}
\end{aligned}$$

The optimum value of model (13) gives the weighting vector w corresponding to the maximum rank position of alternative x_k . It is worth noting that model (13) is a non-linear 0 – 1 programming problem. The weight vector corresponding to the minimum rank position is obtained by solving the minimization problem with the objective as $\min \sum_{i=1}^m y_i + 1$ and following the same set of constraints as in model (13). Subsequently, we can obtain the ranking range $RR(x_i) = [rp^{\min}(x_i), rp^{\max}(x_i)]$ for any alternative x_i .

The ranking range of an alternative provides the decision maker with a view of how the rank of an alternative can vary over the weight space, defined by the incomplete weight information under a normalization condition. This information is crucial to a decision maker planning to manipulate the ranking of several alternatives by strategically selecting a weight vector. From the ranking range of the alternatives, a decision maker can obtain the information on whether the rank position of a particular alternative is achievable or not. If the particular alternative's rank position lies within the ranking range of the corresponding alternative, then it could be achievable when the decision maker strategically manipulates the weights. Therefore, by analysing the ranking range of the alternatives, the decision maker can set a manipulation strategy to obtain the rank of the alternative based on personal interest.

As mentioned, we set w as the strategic weight vector of the attributes set by the decision maker under the given incomplete preference information of the decision maker. From model (11), the strategic manipulative weight can be obtained by solving the following decision making model:

$$\begin{aligned}
\min & \sum_{j=1}^n |w_j - w_j^g| \\
\text{s.t.} & \left\{ \begin{array}{l}
\frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - NI_j)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - NI_j)^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - PI_j)^2}} > \\
\frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - NI_j)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - NI_j)^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - PI_j)^2}} - (1 - y_{ik})M, i = 1, 2, \dots, m, k = i_1, i_2, \dots, i_l \\
\frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - NI_j)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - NI_j)^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - PI_j)^2}} \leq \\
\frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - NI_j)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - NI_j)^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - PI_j)^2}} + y_{ik}M, i = 1, 2, \dots, m, k = i_1, i_2, \dots, i_l \\
\sum_{i=1}^m y_{ik} + 1 = rp^*(x_k), k = i_1, i_2, \dots, i_l \\
\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1 \\
0 \leq w_j \leq 1 \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n \\
w \in Q_w \\
y_{ik} = 1 \text{ or } 0 \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m, k = i_1, i_2, \dots, i_l \\
w_i \geq \beta_i; i = 1, 2, \dots, m
\end{array} \right.
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Solving the mixed non-linear 0 – 1 programming model (14), we obtain the optimal strategic weight of the attributes. The non-linearity arises due to the first and second constraints involving closeness coefficients. Further, the nature of these constraints over the weight space is difficult to determine. Therefore, we need an effective method to find the solution of the optimization model (14). In the midst of many existing methods and algorithms, evolutionary algorithmic (EA) approaches are prominent and more often utilized to obtain the global best solution of this kind of non-linear integer programming problem. In compare to deterministic algorithms, the most significant advantage of EA approach lies in the fact that it can apply to any class of problem without any pre-requisite information about the nature of objective functions and constraints such as continuity and differentiability. Genetic algorithm (GA), being the most prominent one in the family of EAs has been applied widely in practical applications. In this work, we utilize GA to solve the optimization model (14). The rationale behind the choice over other existing approaches is the better capability of GA to solve optimization problem with complex

structure and highly constraint solution space.

4. Genetic Algorithm for Solving Strategic Manipulation in TOPSIS

Genetic Algorithm (GA) is a popular optimization solution method for solving complex optimization problems in many fields such as computer science, engineering, operations research, economics, supply chain, logistics, etc. [49, 50, 51, 52]. Compared to other optimization solution methods, GA has a number of advantages, i.e. ability to work with both discrete and continuous variables, ability to work with large search space, flexibility in handling the constraints and having a very good potential for applying parallel computing techniques [53].

In our proposal, GA is used to solve various optimization problems expressed by Eqs. (13) and (14). It is noted that a GA is a general search principle only and a standard GA for solving every optimization problem does not exist. To effectively use GA, its components such as chromosome encoding, crossover operation, mutation operation, selection operation, and/or structure of GA must be customized to each problem at hand [54]. Typically, each GA has six major components, namely chromosome encoding, crossover operation, mutation operation, evaluation operation, selection operation, and GA structure. Details of these six components will be explained in the next Sections.

4.1. Chromosome Encoding

In GA, chromosome represents a solution to the problem under consideration. For the mixed integer non-linear optimization problems, in this article, each chromosome has two different parts, namely binary part and real part, as illustrated in Table I. The binary part represents the binary variables associated with optimization model under consideration while the real part is associated with the continuous variables of the optimization model. The length of the binary part of the chromosome typically depends on the numbers of binary variables attached to the models. For optimization model (13), the length of binary part is same as the number of alternatives m whereas the model (14) requires $m \times l$ binary variables, where l is the number of alternatives, whose rankings will be manipulated. The length of real part is same for both models and equals to the number of criteria. Note that the both of the optimization models are same in nature, i.e., mixed integer non-linear programming problem and thus, the configuration of the chromosome would be similar except the length of the binary part and constraints on it.

For a generic illustration in the form of an example, we consider the optimization model (14) involving 10 alternatives and 7 criteria and want to set an alternative x_k 's rank, say ($rp^*(x_k) = 6$). Hence, the binary part and the real part of a chromosome for solving this particular optimization problem have 10 ($y_{1k} - y_{10k}$) and 7 ($w_1 - w_7$) genes, respectively. The variables $y_{1k} - y_{10k}$ are binary numbers and variables $w_1 - w_7$ are positive real numbers. The real variables $w_1 - w_7$ have constraints such as $\sum_{i=1}^7 w_i = 1$,

$w \in Q_w$ and $w_i \geq \beta_i$ (named these constraints SW). The binary variables $y_1 - y_{10}$ have constraints in the form $\sum_i^{10} y_{ik} + 1 = rp^*(x_k)$, i.e., $\sum_i^{10} y_i = rp^*(x_k) - 1$ (named this constraint SY). It is noted that we deal with these types of constraints, i.e. SW and SY , when chromosomes are generated, and when crossover operation and mutation operation are implemented; a penalty function will be used to deal with the rest of constraints of the problem when we do evaluation operation.

Table I: Chromosome encoding

Binary part										Real part						
Y1k	Y2k	Y3k	Y4k	Y5k	Y6k	Y7k	Y8k	Y9k	Y10k	w ₁	w ₂	w ₃	w ₄	w ₅	w ₆	w ₇
0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0.02	0.12	0.31	0.25	0.19	0.04	0.07

Chromosomes in initial population of GA are randomly generated in which all variables $y_1 - y_{10}$ and $w_1 - w_7$ are random numbers. However, these variables in a chromosome must satisfy all of the given constraints; otherwise the chromosome would not be feasible. To generate feasible chromosomes, the following steps are proposed:

Step 1: Generate the binary part of the chromosome in which all gene values are 0.

Step 2: Determine the sum constraint of all binary variables, i.e. SY .

Step 3: Randomly select one gene with value of 0 in the selected binary part in Step 1.

Step 4: Replace the value of 0 in the gene selected in Step 3 by the value of 1.

Step 5: Repeat Steps 3-5 SY times.

Step 6: Randomly generate the real part of the chromosome in which all gene values are positive real number ranging from 0 to 1 and satisfy the constraints $w \in Q_w$ and $w_i \geq \beta_i, \forall i$.

Step 7: Determine the sum of all gene values in Step 6.

Step 8: Divide every gene value in the real part in Step 6 by the sum in Step 7. This Step is to ensure that $\sum_i w_i = 1$.

Remark 1. Note that the optimization problem (13) does not have constraint on binary variables (i.e. SY does not exist) and so we do not need Steps 1-5 for chromosome encoding; instead, all binary variables are randomly generated.

4.2. Crossover Operation

Due to constraints involved and to maximize GA performance, three crossover operators are developed; their details will be presented in the subsequent Sections.

4.2.1. Crossover 1

This crossover operation is implemented in the binary part of the parent chromosome only as illustrated in Table II. Due to constraints involved, there is only one parent chromosome and only one offspring chromosome in the operation of crossover 1. Crossover 1 is a four-step procedure:

Step 1: Randomly choose one parent chromosome.

Step 2: Find the binary part of the chromosome chosen in Step 1.

Step 3: Randomly choose one cutting point within the binary part determined in Step 2.

Step 4: Exchange the two pieces as shown in Table II.

Table II: Crossover 1

		Binary part										Real part						
Parent:		y _{1k}	y _{2k}	y _{3k}	y _{4k}	y _{5k}	y _{6k}	y _{7k}	y _{8k}	y _{9k}	y _{10k}	w ₁	w ₂	w ₃	w ₄	w ₅	w ₆	w ₇
			0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0.02	0.12	0.31	0.25	0.19	0.04
		↓																
Offspring:		y _{1k}	y _{2k}	y _{3k}	y _{4k}	y _{5k}	y _{6k}	y _{7k}	y _{8k}	y _{9k}	y _{10k}	w ₁	w ₂	w ₃	w ₄	w ₅	w ₆	w ₇
			1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0.02	0.12	0.31	0.25	0.19	0.04

4.2.2. Crossover 2

Similar to crossover 1, crossover 2 is applied to the real part of the parent chromosome only as illustrated in Table III. Again, due to constraints involved, there is only one parent chromosome and only one offspring chromosome in the operation of crossover 2. To implement crossover 2, the following Steps are proposed.

Step 1: Randomly choose one parent chromosome.

Step 2: Find the real part of the chromosome chosen in Step 1.

Step 3: Randomly choose one cutting point within the real part determined in Step 2.

Step 4: Exchange the two pieces as shown in Table III.

4.2.3. Crossover 3

Like crossovers 1 and 2, crossover 3 is applied to only one part of the parent chromosome, i.e. the real part. And crossover 3 has one parent and one offspring. However, there is no cut-and-swap operation in crossover 3. The following procedure is proposed to implement crossover 3.

Table III: Crossover 2

Parent:	Binary part										Real part						
	y_{1k}	y_{2k}	y_{3k}	y_{4k}	y_{5k}	y_{6k}	y_{7k}	y_{8k}	y_{9k}	y_{10k}	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4	w_5	w_6	w_7
	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0.02	0.12	0.31	0.25	0.19	0.04	0.07

↓

Offspring:	Binary part										Real part						
	y_{1k}	y_{2k}	y_{3k}	y_{4k}	y_{5k}	y_{6k}	y_{7k}	y_{8k}	y_{9k}	y_{10k}	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4	w_5	w_6	w_7
	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0.31	0.25	0.19	0.04	0.07	0.02	0.12

Step 1: Randomly choose one parent chromosome.

Step 2: Find the real part of the chromosome chosen in Step 1.

Step 3: Replace all values in the real part determined in Step 2 by new values generated by Steps 6-8 in Section 4.1, as illustrated in Table IV.

Table IV: Crossover 3

Parent:	Binary part										Real part						
	y_{1k}	y_{2k}	y_{3k}	y_{4k}	y_{5k}	y_{6k}	y_{7k}	y_{8k}	y_{9k}	y_{10k}	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4	w_5	w_6	w_7
	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0.02	0.12	0.31	0.25	0.19	0.04	0.07

↓

Offspring:	Binary part										Real part						
	y_{1k}	y_{2k}	y_{3k}	y_{4k}	y_{5k}	y_{6k}	y_{7k}	y_{8k}	y_{9k}	y_{10k}	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4	w_5	w_6	w_7
	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0.15	0.19	0.3	0.05	0.08	0.22	0.01

Effectiveness of the proposed crossover operators against the traditional crossover operators will be validated in Section 4.6.

4.3. Mutation operation

Due to constraints involved and to maximize the GA performance, three kinds of mutation operations are developed for the GA. In addition, each mutation operator has one parent and one offspring. These three mutation operators will be detailed in the subsequent Sections.

4.3.1. Mutation 1

Mutation 1 is applied to the binary part of the parent chromosome only. As some problems in this article have *SY* constraint and some do not, we consider both scenarios here. If the problem has *SY* constraint, the following procedure is proposed to implement mutation 1.

Step 1: Randomly choose one parent chromosome.

Step 2: Find the binary part of the chromosome chosen in Step 1.

Step 3: Randomly choose one cell (gene) which has the value of 1 within the binary part determined in Step 2.

Step 4: Randomly choose one cell (gene) which has the value of 0 within the binary part determined in Step 2.

Step 5: Swap the two genes selected in Steps 3-4 as shown in Table V.

Table V: Mutation 1 (scenario 1)

Parent:	Binary part										Real part						
	y_{1k}	y_{2k}	y_{3k}	y_{4k}	y_{5k}	y_{6k}	y_{7k}	y_{8k}	y_{9k}	y_{10k}	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4	w_5	w_6	w_7
	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0.02	0.12	0.31	0.25	0.19	0.04	0.07

↓

Offspring:	Binary part										Real part						
	y_{1k}	y_{2k}	y_{3k}	y_{4k}	y_{5k}	y_{6k}	y_{7k}	y_{8k}	y_{9k}	y_{10k}	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4	w_5	w_6	w_7
	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0.02	0.12	0.31	0.25	0.19	0.04	0.07

If the problem does not have SY constraint, the following procedure is proposed to implement mutation 1.

Step 1: Randomly choose one parent chromosome.

Step 2: Find the binary part of the chromosome chosen in Step 1.

Step 3: Randomly choose one gene within the binary part determined in Step 2.

Step 4: Flip the value of the gene selected in Step 3 as illustrated in Table VI.

Table VI: Mutation 1 (scenario 2)

Parent:	Binary part										Real part						
	y_{1k}	y_{2k}	y_{3k}	y_{4k}	y_{5k}	y_{6k}	y_{7k}	y_{8k}	y_{9k}	y_{10k}	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4	w_5	w_6	w_7
	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0.02	0.12	0.31	0.25	0.19	0.04	0.07

↓

Offspring:	Binary part										Real part						
	y_{1k}	y_{2k}	y_{3k}	y_{4k}	y_{5k}	y_{6k}	y_{7k}	y_{8k}	y_{9k}	y_{10k}	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4	w_5	w_6	w_7
	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0.02	0.12	0.31	0.25	0.19	0.04	0.07

4.3.2. Mutation 2

Like crossover 2, mutation 2 is applied to the real part of the parent chromosome only. Due to constraint involved, the following procedure is proposed to implement mutation 2.

Step 1: Randomly choose one parent chromosome.

Step 2: Find the real part of the chromosome chosen in Step 1.

Step 3: Randomly choose two genes within the real part determined in Step 2.

Step 4: Swap the two genes selected in Step 3 as shown in VII.

Table VII: Mutation 2

Parent:	Binary part										Real part						
	y _{1k}	y _{2k}	y _{3k}	y _{4k}	y _{5k}	y _{6k}	y _{7k}	y _{8k}	y _{9k}	y _{10k}	w ₁	w ₂	w ₃	w ₄	w ₅	w ₆	w ₇
	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0.02	0.12	0.31	0.25	0.19	0.04	0.07
Offspring:	Binary part										Real part						
	y _{1k}	y _{2k}	y _{3k}	y _{4k}	y _{5k}	y _{6k}	y _{7k}	y _{8k}	y _{9k}	y _{10k}	w ₁	w ₂	w ₃	w ₄	w ₅	w ₆	w ₇
	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0.02	0.19	0.31	0.25	0.12	0.04	0.07

4.3.3. Mutation 3

Mutation 3 is also applied to the real part of the parent chromosome only. Due to constraint involved and to increase the exploitation of the GA, the following procedure is proposed to implement mutation 3.

Step 1: Randomly choose one parent chromosome.

Step 2: Find the real part of the parent chromosome chosen in Step 1.

Step 3: Randomly generate increment step size in terms of percentage (p), e.g. $p = 10$ percent.

Step 4: Randomly choose two genes within the real part determined in Step 2.

Step 5: Reduce the value of the first gene selected in Step 4 by p percent generated in Step 3 as illustrated in Table VIII.

Step 6: Add the reduction made in Step 5 to the value of the second gene selected in Step 4 as illustrated in Table VIII.

Table VIII: Mutation 3

Parent:	Binary part										Real part						
	y _{1k}	y _{2k}	y _{3k}	y _{4k}	y _{5k}	y _{6k}	y _{7k}	y _{8k}	y _{9k}	y _{10k}	w ₁	w ₂	w ₃	w ₄	w ₅	w ₆	w ₇
	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0.02	0.12	0.31	0.25	0.19	0.04	0.07
	↓																
Offspring:	Binary part										Real part						
	y _{1k}	y _{2k}	y _{3k}	y _{4k}	y _{5k}	y _{6k}	y _{7k}	y _{8k}	y _{9k}	y _{10k}	w ₁	w ₂	w ₃	w ₄	w ₅	w ₆	w ₇
	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0.02	0.12	0.28	0.25	0.19	0.07	0.07

4.4. Evaluation Operation

Quality of chromosomes/solutions is evaluated through the objective function value (*OFV*) and the penalty value (*PV*). As mentioned in Section 4.1, besides *SY* and *SW* constraints, the optimization problems under consideration have other constraints, and to deal with them, the concept of penalty function is used. For each violated constraint, we add corresponding penalty to *PV*. For maximization problems, the fitness value of a chromosome is calculated by Eq. (15).

$$F = OFV - PV \quad (15)$$

For minimization problems, the fitness value of a chromosome is calculated by Eq. (16). It should be noted that for maximization problems, the larger *F*, the better; but for minimization problems, the smaller *F*, the better.

$$F = OFV + PV \quad (16)$$

For example, in the case of the optimization model (13), the *OFV* becomes $\sum_{i=1}^m y_i + 1$ while for the optimization model (14) the *OFV* become $\sum_{j=1}^n |w_j - w_j^g|$. Regarding the penalty value (*PV*), after testing several penalty functions to handle the constraints of the problems, we ended up using the following function for the optimization problem (13):

$$PV = 2 \times \sum_{i=1}^m C_{1i} + C_{2i}$$

where

$$C_{1i} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if constraint Eq.(17) is not satisfied for } i \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$C_{2i} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if constraint Eq.(18) is not satisfied for } i \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - NI_j)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - NI_j)^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - PI_j)^2}} > \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - NI_j)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - NI_j)^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - PI_j)^2}} - (1-y_i)M \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - NI_j)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - NI_j)^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - PI_j)^2}} \leq \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - NI_j)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - NI_j)^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - PI_j)^2}} + y_i M \quad (18)$$

In the case of optimization problem (14), the nature and formulation remain same and it could be written as follows:

$$PV = 2 \times \sum_{\substack{i \in \{1,2,\dots,m\} \\ k \in \{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_l\}}} C_{1i}^k + C_{2i}^k$$

where

$$C_{1i}^k = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if constraint Eq.(19) is not satisfied for } i \text{ and } k \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$C_{2i}^k = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if constraint Eq.(20) is not satisfied for } i \text{ and } k \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - NI_j)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - NI_j)^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - PI_j)^2}} > \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - NI_j)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - NI_j)^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - PI_j)^2}} - (1-y_{ik})M \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - NI_j)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - NI_j)^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij}w_j - PI_j)^2}} \leq \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - NI_j)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - NI_j)^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{kj}w_j - PI_j)^2}} + y_{ik} M \quad (20)$$

4.5. Selection Operation

In this article, to select chromosomes from one generation to pass to the next one (new population), we use Roulette Wheel selection method in which a new population is selected based on the probability distribution associated with the fitness values of chromosomes [55]. Elite strategy, in which the best chromosome in one generation is guaranteed to pass to the next generation, is also used in the selection

process.

As can be seen from the algorithm structure of the proposed GA in Figure 1, offspring chromosomes (children) can be generated by three crossovers and three mutations. The number of offspring chromosomes in each generation depends on the crossover and mutation parameters (c_1 , c_2 , c_3 , m_1 , m_2 , and m_3) of the proposed GA - which is $c_1 + c_2 + c_3 + m_1 + m_2 + m_3$. It should be noted that the rates of crossover and mutation operators (c_1 , c_2 , c_3 , m_1 , m_2 , and m_3) in this paper are in terms of the number of parent chromosomes to be done crossover and mutation, respectively. In this research, to maximize the performance of the proposed GA, its parameters are systematically tuned by the Taguchi experimental design method [56] as shown in Section 4.6, and the selected parameters are shown in Table IX.

Table IX: Selected parameters of the proposed GA

ps	c_1	c_2	c_3	m_1	m_2	m_3	rc
50	30	50	30	70	30	50	100

Figure 1 also shows that in the proposed GA, offspring chromosomes (children) and parent chromosomes are competing with each other, based on fitness value and Roulette Wheel selection rule [55], to be selected to go to the next generation (old and new chromosomes are competing with each other). In each generation, there are $ps + c_1 + c_2 + c_3 + m_1 + m_2 + m_3$ chromosomes (both parent and children chromosomes) to be evaluated and only population size chromosomes will be selected to go to the next generation to keep the population size constant. The selected chromosomes will replace the old population in the previous generation.

4.6. Genetic Algorithm Structure

A novel GA structure (see Fig. 1) for improving its search capability in which, unlike the traditional GA, the proposed GA has two loops. The small loop is similar to the loop in the traditional GA and the big loop is similar to the loop in multi-start algorithms.

In Fig. 1, the letter A represents the adaptive restart condition that is the number of generations within which the GA could not find a better solution, and the letter G is the total number of generations of the GA. Thanks to the big loop, the proposed GA can restart the search process if the GA cannot find a chromosome, which is better than the one achieved so far, after a pre-set number of generations. Thereby, the global search capability of the proposed GA is enhanced; in other words, the proposed GA has a better exploration capacity, compared to the traditional GA. In addition, the proposed GA has three different crossover operations and three different mutation operations which apply to different parts of parent chromosomes. Due to multiple crossover/mutation operations, the proposed GA has a better exploitation capacity, compared to the traditional GA.

To validate the effectiveness of the proposed GA, with the innovations in crossover/mutation operators, chromosome encoding, and the algorithm structure, we conducted 250 experiments (25 problems

Table X: Experimental levels of the parameters of the proposed GA

No	Parameter	Code	Experimental level		
			1	2	3
1	Population size	ps	50	100	150
2	Crossover 1	c_1	30	50	70
3	Crossover 2	c_2	30	50	70
4	Crossover 3	c_3	30	50	70
5	Mutation 1	m_1	30	50	70
6	Mutation 2	m_2	30	50	70
7	Mutation 3	m_3	30	50	70
8	Restart condition	rc	50	100	150

$\times 10$ independent runs) and compared its performance with the performance of the traditional GA. The 25 problems are based on the optimization model (13) and data set from Table XIV. To maximize the performance, parameter set of the proposed GA, including population size (ps), rate of crossover 1 (c_1), rate of crossover 2 (c_2), rate of crossover 3 (c_3), rate of mutation 1 (m_1), rate of mutation 2 (m_2), rate of mutation 3 (m_3), and restart condition (rc), was systematically tuned by the Taguchi experimental design method [56]. It is noted that the rates of crossover and mutation operators ($c_1, c_2, c_3, m_1, m_2,$ and m_3) in this paper are in terms of the number of parent chromosomes to be done crossover and muta-

Figure 1: GA structure

tion, respectively. In addition, the restart condition of the proposed GA (rc) is the number of successive generations within which the quality of the best chromosome obtained so far has not been improved. For example, when rc is equal to 50, the proposed GA will restart its search process if it cannot find a better solution after 50 successive generations. Based on its complexity, problem 2 (among 25 problems mentioned above) was chosen to be used to conduct Taguchi experiments to select the parameter set of the proposed GA.

Table XI: Taguchi experimental layout and experimental results

Experiment	Parameter								Computing time (s)	Experimental result		
	ps	c_1	c_2	c_3	m_1	m_2	m_3	rc		Run 1	Run 2	Run 3
1	50	30	30	30	30	30	30	50	60	23	23	23
2	50	30	30	30	50	50	50	100	60	23	23	19
3	50	30	30	30	70	70	70	150	60	23	23	23
4	50	50	50	50	30	30	30	100	60	13	24	23
5	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	150	60	16	18	23
6	50	50	50	50	70	70	70	50	60	23	23	23
7	50	70	70	70	30	30	30	150	60	14	22	13
8	50	70	70	70	50	50	50	50	60	18	18	23
9	50	70	70	70	70	70	70	100	60	23	13	16
10	100	30	50	70	30	50	70	50	60	17	17	17
11	100	30	50	70	50	70	30	100	60	13	23	23
12	100	30	50	70	70	30	50	150	60	23	23	23
13	100	50	70	30	30	50	70	100	60	23	23	13
14	100	50	70	30	50	70	30	150	60	17	15	15
15	100	50	70	30	70	30	50	50	60	14	20	22
16	100	70	30	50	30	50	70	150	60	19	23	17
17	100	70	30	50	50	70	30	50	60	13	14	14
18	100	70	30	50	70	30	50	100	60	23	23	21
19	150	30	70	50	30	70	50	50	60	15	17	17
20	150	30	70	50	50	30	70	100	60	14	14	17
21	150	30	70	50	70	50	30	150	60	16	14	14
22	150	50	30	70	30	70	50	100	60	14	13	13
23	150	50	30	70	50	30	70	150	60	14	14	15
24	150	50	30	70	70	50	30	50	60	13	13	13
25	150	70	50	30	30	70	50	150	60	14	15	18
26	150	70	50	30	50	30	70	50	60	13	18	23
27	150	70	50	30	70	50	30	100	60	15	21	21

Experimental levels of 8 parameters of the proposed GA are shown in Table X. Taguchi experimental layout and experimental results are shown in Table XI. As can be seen from Tables X-XI, each parameter has three experimental levels, and 27 experiments are required. To make a fair comparison, the computing time in each experiment was set to be exactly the same (60 seconds), and each experiment was repeated 3 times (3 independent runs), as shown in Table XI. It should be noted that the programming language and the machine used in this research were Matlab and laptop computer (processor: Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-6200U CPU @ 2.30GHz), respectively. Minitab software was used to generate the main effect plots that represent the effect of the parameters on the GA performance, as shown in Figure 2. Based on the results on the Figure 2, the parameter set of the proposed GA was selected as shown in Table IX.

To validate the effectiveness of the proposed GA, we compared its performance with the performance of the traditional GA. It is noted that the traditional GA is exactly the same as the proposed GA except

the crossover, mutation, and restart mechanism. More specifically, the traditional GA has one crossover as shown in Figure 3, in which the inputs of the crossover are two random parent chromosomes and the outputs are two offspring chromosomes. Due to the constraints of the problems, the traditional GA has two mutations: mutation 1 as shown in Figure 4 and mutation 2 as shown in Table VII (exactly the same as mutation 2 of the proposed GA). In addition, the traditional GA does not have the restart mechanism as shown in Figure 1. To make a fair comparison, parameter set of the traditional GA, including the population size (ps), rate of crossover (c), rate of mutation 1 (m1), and rate of mutation 2 (m2), was also systematically tuned by the Taguchi experimental design method [56]. The selected parameters of the traditional GA are shown in Table XII.

Performances of the proposed GA and the traditional GA in solving 25 problems are shown in Table

Figure 2: Main effect plots of the parameters of the proposed GA

	Binary part										Real part						
	y_1	y_2	y_3	y_4	y_5	y_6	y_7	y_8	y_9	y_{10}	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4	w_5	w_6	w_7
Parent 1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0.02	0.12	0.31	0.25	0.19	0.04	0.07
Parent 2	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0.03	0.14	0.21	0.23	0.19	0.14	0.06
↓																	
Offspring 1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0.03	0.14	0.21	0.23	0.19	0.14	0.06
Offspring 2	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0.02	0.12	0.31	0.25	0.19	0.04	0.07

Figure 3: Crossover of the traditional GA

Table XII: Selected parameters of the traditional GA

ps	c	m_1	m_2
100	30	30	30

XIII. Each algorithm was run for 10 times (10 independent runs) and computing time in each run was 60 seconds. The minimum, average, maximum, and standard deviation of the objective function values achieved by the two algorithms are reported in Table XIII. It should be noted that all 25 problems here are the maximization problems; so, the larger the objective function value, the better. Experimental data from Table XIV indicates that the proposed GA performed much better than the traditional GA, i.e., 82.85% better, on average. This large performance gap shows that the tradition GA is more likely to get stuck in the local optima of the problems (highly constrained optimization problems).

5. Numerical analysis

This section accomplishes a numerical analysis to show how the rank of an alternative may vary over the weight space in the following MADM problem.

Consider the 25 universities from Times Higher Education world universities ranking as a set of alternatives and denote it by $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{25}\}$. These alternatives are ranked based on the following criteria:

- C_1 : Teaching (the learning environment)
- C_2 : Research (volume income and reputation)
- C_3 : Citations (Research influence)

Figure 4: Mutation 1 of the traditional GA

Table XIII: Performance comparison

Problem	Computing time (s)	Traditional GA				Proposed GA			
		Min	Average	Max	Std	Min	Average	Max	Std
1	60	13.00	13.00	13.00	0.00	20.00	20.20	22.00	0.60
2	60	13.00	13.00	13.00	0.00	23.00	23.00	23.00	0.00
3	60	13.00	13.80	14.00	0.40	25.00	25.00	25.00	0.00
4	60	13.00	13.00	13.00	0.00	17.00	22.40	23.00	1.80
5	60	13.00	13.20	15.00	0.60	23.00	23.00	23.00	0.00
6	60	13.00	13.00	13.00	0.00	18.00	24.00	25.00	2.19
7	60	13.00	13.00	13.00	0.00	11.00	13.40	15.00	1.20
8	60	13.00	13.00	13.00	0.00	22.00	23.20	25.00	0.98
9	60	12.00	12.70	13.00	0.46	23.00	24.00	25.00	1.00
10	60	13.00	13.00	13.00	0.00	24.00	24.00	24.00	0.00
11	60	12.00	12.60	13.00	0.49	23.00	23.60	25.00	0.92
12	60	12.00	12.90	13.00	0.30	25.00	25.00	25.00	0.00
13	60	13.00	13.00	13.00	0.00	25.00	25.00	25.00	0.00
14	60	12.00	12.90	13.00	0.30	24.00	24.00	24.00	0.00
15	60	13.00	13.00	13.00	0.00	24.00	24.00	24.00	0.00
16	60	13.00	13.00	13.00	0.00	24.00	24.90	25.00	0.30
17	60	12.00	12.90	13.00	0.30	25.00	25.00	25.00	0.00
18	60	13.00	13.00	13.00	0.00	25.00	25.00	25.00	0.00
19	60	12.00	12.90	13.00	0.30	25.00	25.00	25.00	0.00
20	60	12.00	12.90	13.00	0.30	25.00	25.00	25.00	0.00
21	60	13.00	13.00	13.00	0.00	25.00	25.00	25.00	0.00
22	60	13.00	13.10	14.00	0.30	25.00	25.00	25.00	0.00
23	60	13.00	13.00	13.00	0.00	25.00	25.00	25.00	0.00
24	60	12.00	12.80	13.00	0.40	25.00	25.00	25.00	0.00
25	60	12.00	13.00	14.00	0.45	25.00	25.00	25.00	0.00

- C_4 : Industry income (knowledge transfer)
- C_5 : International outlook (staff, students and research)

It is assumed that all the criteria are equally important, i.e., the weight vector $w = (0.2, 0.2, 0.2, 0.2, 0.2)$ and all the criteria belong to benefit criteria category. First, we utilize the vector normalization procedure described in Eq.(1) to normalize the rating of the alternatives. Then utilizing the steps 2-6, we compute the closeness coefficient of the alternatives $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{25}\}$ and the results listed in the Table XIV with the rank order of the alternatives'. Apparently, x_5 is the best alternative while x_{18} is the worst alternative.

At earlier stage, we assume that no preference about the weight space is given. That is, we only know that weight vector are coming from n -dimensional simplex. In order to obtain an overview about how the rank of an alternative varies over the weight space, we compute the ranking range for each of the alternatives by solving mixed integer non-linear optimization model (12) and it's minimization version where objective function of (12) would be minimized. In particular, we have utilized GA, outlined in the Section IV to find the solution of these models. The results are summarized in the Table XV with the corresponding weight vectors. It is noted that $w_{\min}(x_i)$ denotes the weight vector corresponding to the $rp^{\min}(x_i)$ and $w_{\max}(x_i)$ represents the weight vector associated with $rp^{\max}(x_i)$. For example, in Table XV the first entry corresponding to the alternative x_1 , i.e., $[rp^{\min}(x_1)rp^{\max}(x_1)] = [1, 7]$ represents

Table XIV: Ratings of 25 universities and their ranking based on closeness coefficient

x_i	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	C_5	Closeness Coefficient (CC_i)
x_1	86.7	99.5	99.1	63.7	95	0.5816(6)
x_2	87.8	97.8	97.5	51.5	93	0.4693(11)
x_3	90.3	97.5	99.5	92.6	59.7	0.6780(4)
x_4	89.1	96.7	99.9	60.5	77.6	0.4945(10)
x_5	87.3	91.9	100	88.4	87.6	0.8089(1)
x_6	84.2	98.4	99.7	46.4	79.7	0.3801(13)
x_7	85.7	93.9	99.6	58	78.7	0.4625(12)
x_8	81.7	88.7	96.7	71.6	96.6	0.6380(5)
x_9	85.3	90.1	99.4	39.8	69.6	0.2837(22)
x_{10}	76.4	92	94.3	60.3	98.1	0.5258(8)
x_{11}	83.7	90.1	98.5	56.9	61.3	0.3773(14)
x_{12}	86.7	87	98.4	45.1	64.6	0.2929(19)
x_{13}	76.1	88.1	98.4	95.8	70.6	0.7185(2)
x_{14}	82.2	83.3	98.8	41.3	76.6	0.2914(20)
x_{15}	80.7	88.1	97.9	48.6	59.5	0.2859(21)
x_{16}	74.4	88.2	94.6	41.2	94.6	0.3648(15)
x_{17}	80.7	80.6	98.3	100	62.5	0.6845(3)
x_{18}	77.4	84.5	99.8	37.5	64.5	0.2118(25)
x_{19}	76.2	86.6	97.6	34.6	69.2	0.2159(24)
x_{20}	72.6	86.7	96.9	78.2	59.2	0.5356(7)
x_{21}	77.2	86.3	95.7	46.2	55.8	0.2382(23)
x_{22}	77.4	88.2	81.3	61.9	95.8	0.5153(9)
x_{23}	74.6	84.8	92.6	46.5	80.1	0.3141(17)
x_{24}	65.8	83.7	99.7	50.4	79.1	0.3367(16)
x_{25}	71.8	72	94.9	33.7	92.2	0.2990(18)

the ranking range of the alternative x_1 when no preference information of the attributes' weights was not provided by the decision maker. Further, the lower rank position $rp^{\min}(x_1) = 1$ is obtained at the attributes weight vector $w_{\min}(x_1) = (0.0543, 0.2543, 0.3431, 0.0341, 0.3142)$ and upper ranking position $rp^{\max}(x_1) = 7$ is obtained at $w_{\max}(x_1) = (0.0115, 0.2911, 0.3966, 0.2482, 0.0525)$.

In the existing subject and objective approaches of weight vector settings, we assume that decision maker is honest and intend to set attributes weight in aim of finding an optimal ranking of the alternatives. However, a decision maker may be dishonest or intend to set the attributes weight strategically to fulfil his/her desire. Table XV gives an overview how the rank of different alternatives can vary over the attributes weight space. It also helps the decision maker in strategic manipulation of ranking of the alternatives. Now, we illustrate few strategic manipulation scenarios in which a decision maker aims to set the attribute weights to achieve his/her preference.

Let w^g be the objective weight of the attribute, and rp the initial ranking position of the alternatives. Initially, we assumed that the criteria are equally important i.e., $w^0 = (1/5, 1/5, 1/5, 1/5, 1/5)$ and in this ranking position of the alternatives has already been obtained using TOPSIS in Table XIV. We denote strategically manipulated ranking position of the alternatives by rp^* . We describe few manipulation scenarios:

- Suppose a decision maker intends to manipulate the rank of the alternative x_2 . From Table XIV, it is clear that $rp(x_2) = 11$. The decision maker desires the ranking position of the alternative $rp^*(x_2) = 6$. In other words, the decision maker wants to manipulate the ranking position of the

Table XV: Ratings of 25 universities and their ranking based on closeness coefficient

x_i	$[rp^{\min}(x_i)rp^{\max}(x_i)]$	w_{min}	w_{max}
x_1	[1, 7]	[0.0543, 0.2543, 0.3431, 0.0341, 0.3142]	[0.0115, 0.2911, 0.3966, 0.2482, 0.0525]
x_2	[1, 14]	[0.3930, 0.1828, 0.2586, 0.0093, 0.1563]	[0.0479, 0.0542, 0.5630, 0.2741, 0.0607]
x_3	[1, 22]	[0.2050, 0.3043, 0.0472, 0.3411, 0.1025]	[0.0722, 0.0781, 0.2482, 0.0224, 0.5790]
x_4	[1, 11]	[0.4702, 0.2231, 0.2346, 0.0211, 0.0510]	[0.1425, 0.1079, 0.1793, 0.2525, 0.3178]
x_5	[1, 8]	[0.1553, 0.0427, 0.4051, 0.2110, 0.1858]	[0.2012, 0.1196, 0.0830, 0.0339, 0.5623]
x_6	[3, 18]	[0.0877, 0.5263, 0.1893, 0.0408, 0.1560]	[0.0710, 0.0819, 0.0405, 0.4009, 0.4056]
x_7	[5, 13]	[0.2200, 0.2125, 0.4418, 0.0679, 0.0579]	[0.1530, 0.0698, 0.0916, 0.2609, 0.4246]
x_8	[1, 18]	[0.0889, 0.1209, 0.3992, 0.0649, 0.3260]	[0.0682, 0.0339, 0.8517, 0.0109, 0.0353]
x_9	[8, 23]	[0.3321, 0.2478, 0.3487, 0.0256, 0.0458]	[0.0111, 0.2943, 0.1572, 0.3321, 0.2054]
x_{10}	[2, 18]	[0.1327, 0.3910, 0.0835, 0.0692, 0.3237]	[0.5546, 0.1071, 0.1298, 0.1342, 0.0743]
x_{11}	[7, 23]	[0.2163, 0.0868, 0.6468, 0.0417, 0.0084]	[0.1138, 0.0845, 0.3707, 0.0818, 0.3491]
x_{12}	[7, 22]	[0.5564, 0.2023, 0.1295, 0.0656, 0.0461]	[0.1131, 0.3004, 0.0956, 0.1453, 0.3455]
x_{13}	[1, 19]	[0.0531, 0.0749, 0.4826, 0.2679, 0.1215]	[0.4609, 0.1397, 0.0309, 0.0100, 0.3585]
x_{14}	[8, 23]	[0.2217, 0.1044, 0.5238, 0.0266, 0.1235]	[0.0965, 0.3483, 0.0693, 0.2787, 0.2072]
x_{15}	[12, 24]	[0.5214, 0.4141, 0.0140, 0.0182, 0.0322]	[0.0673, 0.1032, 0.3672, 0.1360, 0.3263]
x_{16}	[4, 24]	[0.0506, 0.1011, 0.2707, 0.0315, 0.5462]	[0.2187, 0.0887, 0.4754, 0.1995, 0.0177]
x_{17}	[1, 25]	[0.1461, 0.0279, 0.4035, 0.3655, 0.0571]	[0.1745, 0.3766, 0.2489, 0.0120, 0.1881]
x_{18}	[14, 25]	[0.2132, 0.1640, 0.6001, 0.0108, 0.0118]	[0.0424, 0.1135, 0.2670, 0.2882, 0.2890]
x_{19}	[17, 25]	[0.1354, 0.1686, 0.1696, 0.0713, 0.4551]	[0.3035, 0.2338, 0.1117, 0.2013, 0.1497]
x_{20}	[5, 25]	[0.0213, 0.2558, 0.2974, 0.3169, 0.1086]	[0.3184, 0.3334, 0.0130, 0.0098, 0.3254]
x_{21}	[18, 25]	[0.2541, 0.3426, 0.1544, 0.2081, 0.0409]	[0.1454, 0.1905, 0.3646, 0.0288, 0.2708]
x_{22}	[4, 25]	[0.4128, 0.0518, 0.0719, 0.1578, 0.3056]	[0.1656, 0.0801, 0.5391, 0.0911, 0.1241]
x_{23}	[10, 25]	[0.1555, 0.1200, 0.1579, 0.0465, 0.5202]	[0.0416, 0.0796, 0.6040, 0.1478, 0.1270]
x_{24}	[11, 25]	[0.0703, 0.0667, 0.5487, 0.1099, 0.2044]	[0.5917, 0.0998, 0.1492, 0.1029, 0.0564]
x_{25}	[6, 25]	[0.0763, 0.0552, 0.4089, 0.0245, 0.4351]	[0.4325, 0.3988, 0.0308, 0.0603, 0.0776]

alternative x_2 by settings strategically the attribute weights to improve the ranking position of the university x_2 . We have employed strategic weight manipulation model (14) and obtained the strategic weight vector $w^* = (0.2098, 0.2215, 0.2067, 0.1315, 0.2306)$ to achieve this purpose.

- Let x_9 be the alternative that the decision maker wishes for manipulation. Note that the current ranking position of the alternative is $rp(x_3) = 4$. Further, the decision maker prefers to set the alternative x_2 's ranking position as $rp^*(x_3) = 8$, i.e., the decision maker dishonestly wants to depress the ranking position of the alternatives by manipulating attribute weight strategically. We utilized the strategic weight manipulation model (14) and obtained the strategic weight vector $w^* = (0.1989, 0.1999, 0.1993, 0.1509, 0.2510)$ to achieve this purpose.
- Let the decision maker wants to manipulate the alternatives' set $\{x_6, x_{15}\}$. The current ranking position of the alternatives' $rp = \{13, 9\}$. The decision maker desires to set the ranking position of the alternatives' as $rp^* = \{14, 18\}$. That is he/she wants to improve the ranking position of the both of alternatives x_{15} and to depress the ranking position of the alternative x_6 . We implemented the strategic weight manipulation model (14) and found the strategic weight vector $w^* = (0.1905, 0.2010, 0.2007, 0.2163, 0.1915)$ to achieve this purpose.
- Let $\{x_1, x_4\}$ be the alternatives that the decision maker seeks to manipulate together. Initial ranking of the alternatives' is $rp = \{6, 10\}$. Suppose the decision maker desires to set the ranking position as $rp^* = \{3, 8\}$ by strategically manipulating the weight information. In other words, he/she

wants to improve the ranking of both of the alternatives. We utilize the strategic weight manipulation model (14) and obtained the strategic weight vector $w^* = (0.2060, 0.2670, 0.2014, 0.1241, 0.2015)$ to achieve this purpose.

So far, we have not provided any preference information over the attribute weights except the fact that it is coming from the n -dimensional simplex. It can be observed from Table XV that sometimes weight of the particular attributes becomes negligible. That means the information regarding that attribute contributes very little in the final ranking position of the alternatives. To preserve all attribute importance to some extent, decision maker provides preferences over the weight information of the attributes. In this sequel, the decision maker sets the constraint over the attribute weight space that all the component should be greater than or equal to 0.1, i.e., $Q_w = \{(w_1, w_2, \dots, w_6) : w_j \geq 0.1 \forall j, \sum_{j=1}^6 w_j = 1\}$. With this new preference information of the attributes' weight, we have employed the optimization model 13 to find the ranking range of all the alternatives and the results are depicted in the Fig. 5. It is observed from Fig. 5 that with the decision maker preference information, most of the alternatives' ranking range have been changed significantly. Further, we note that for any alternative x_i , the ranking ranges with decision maker preference information and without any preference information satisfies the following relationship: $[rp_{new}^{\min}(x_i), rp_{new}^{\max}(x_i)] \subset [rp_{old}^{\min}(x_i), rp_{old}^{\max}(x_i)]$, where the suffixes *new* and *old* in the ranking ranges indicates the range with decision maker's preference information and without preference information, respectively. In other words, when the preference information on the weight space is given, the ranking ranges of the alternatives shrinks.

On the other hand, the results in the case of strategically setting the weight vectors to manipulate the ranking of the alternatives do not change as the optimal strategic weight vectors satisfy the additional weight constraint dictated by the decision maker's preference on the weight information.

Figure 5: (a) changing of lower ranking position of the alternatives with weight information; (b) changing of upper ranking position of the alternatives with weight information

6. Conclusion

In this study, we have considered the strategic weight manipulation strategy under a TOPSIS based group decision making method. Inspired by Dong et al.'s [35] weight manipulation model, we have translated the weight manipulation strategy into optimization model (13), which is non-linear and mixed integer. The optimization model allows us to find ranking range of the alternatives. The ranking range allows us to visualize the variation of the ranking of the alternatives over the weight space. Further, we have considered the incomplete weight information of the attributes given by the decision maker at the time of manipulation of the weight strategically, which allows the decision maker to come up with the strategic weight according to personal preference. The incorporation of weight information in the optimization model provides a decision maker with the flexibility of setting the weights according to individual preference over the weight information. As the optimization model for strategically setting the weights being non-linear and mixed integer, we have developed a GA-based algorithm to find the solution. Finally, we have presented an actual example in which we illustrate the working of this method. The effect of incomplete attributes weight information has been discussed.

Although this paper has focused on a TOPSIS based multi-attribute decision making method, the generalized optimization model (11) can be utilized in the strategic manipulation of the weights of the other multi-attribute methods such as VIKOR, QUALIFLEX, ELECTRE, and PROMETHEE. In future, it would be interesting to investigate the strategic weight manipulation in the fuzzy settings of the above mentioned multi-attribute decision making methods. It is worthwhile to mention that such fuzzy settings would be much more complicated than the traditional crisp settings proposed in this work due to presence of highly incomplete and imperfect operational laws of the fuzzy quantities.

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